

Towards Edible Gas Sensors to Reduce Food Waste

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Abstract: According to the United Nations Environment Programme report on the Food Waste Index, around 18 % of the world's food production is being wasted along the food chain. Moreover, food waste also accounts for about 10% of the world's greenhouse gas emissions. For these reasons, food waste represents a universal challenge for the rising global hunger and climate change. In this context, technologies that constantly evaluate the state of the food are required to prevent its spoilage and consequent waste. The detection of low concentrations (orders of a few ppm) of the gases produced upon food deterioration, such as methane, ethylene, and biogenic amines, can be used as early indicators of food deterioration. One of the main limitations of gas sensors used for this purpose is their poor compatibility with food packaging, as they are composed of toxic or non-biocompatible materials. In our research, we developed gas sensors based on Organic Field Effect Transistors whose components are entirely edible. For these reasons, these environmentally friendly sensors can be safely introduced into food packaging without being harmful, even in case of ingestion.